

Integrated Library Management System Deployment: An Experimentation Requirement and Procedure with Koha

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Abstract

The experimental case study assessed the functionality and workflows of Koha, an open-source integrated library system (ILS), and determined the feasibility of implementing it in library environments based on the necessary installation, configuration, data migration, and staff training requirements. The study followed the system development lifecycle. Implementation and test plans were created, and an installation platform was selected. Koha was installed using prerequisites on a Linux server, using system settings, modules, metadata standards, and tools. Koha version 22.04 on a Linux server running Xubuntu 20.04 LTS which included Apache, MySQL, Perl modules, and Solr 8 for indexing was used. Sample data were obtained from the Library of Congress bibliographic database with bibliographic, holdings, and authority records. Koha was successfully installed with 100 sample MARC records loaded from the Library of Congress. Testing during deployment showed all circulation, cataloguing, acquisition, and administration functions operating correctly. Relationships were maintained between authority, bibliographic,

holdings, and item records demonstrating robust data models. The study concluded that the experimental case study offers a valuable framework for libraries seeking to implement Koha ILS and leverage its capabilities for electronic content management. The process emphasized essential stages involved in installation, data migration, configuration, integration, and testing. The study recommended that libraries should allocate budgets for customizing Koha usability. Library schools should incorporate open-source ILS courses to extend the knowledge and skills acquisition to students and the like.

Keywords: *Integrated Library Management System, Koha Experimentation, Library Setting, Open-Source Software, Library Automation, MARC Records*

Introduction

The significance of digital content management has witnessed a notable rise in the contemporary Era of information explosion (Adesola and Olla, 2018; Ghosh and Saha, 2022). Libraries and other institutions have the responsibility of safeguarding and facilitating access to expanding repositories of digital resources (Khan, 2017; Jaba and Panneerselvam, 2018; Madhav et al., 2023). Integrated library systems (ILS) such as (give some examples) offer the necessary framework for effectively managing both digital materials and conventional print collections.

Koha is a highly prevalent open-source Integrated Library System (ILS) solution. Koha, which originated in New Zealand, offers a comprehensive range of

features for various library functions such as acquisitions, cataloguing, circulation, and reference and serials management. One notable advantage of Koha lies in its inherent adaptability, as highlighted by McGarvey (2018) and Niranjana et al. (2021). Libraries can extensively tailor Koha, an open-source system, to meet their individualised requirements. Nevertheless, the implementation of a new Integrated Library System (ILS) necessitates meticulous strategizing and implementation. The successful implementation of a system heavily relies on the meticulous execution of installation, configuration, deployment, and testing processes (Ghosh and Saha, 2022; Madhav et al., 2023).

Every library should deploy infrastructure that would

enable the acquisition, organisation, and provision of digital information resources to cope with the desires and needs of information and communication technology-savvy users. The emergence and ever-growing usefulness and ease of use being provided and provisioned by the various information technologies are the basis for the organisation and dissemination of digital information contents by libraries through various technologies, including Koha ILS.

Nevertheless, library institutions have many obstacles such like..... in the realm of digital content management (Omopupa *et al.*, 2020; Jamogha *et al.*, 2022). Scalable systems are necessary due to the presence of many digital object types, evolving standards, and increasing amounts of information resources. It is generally believed that the utilisation of proprietary Integrated Library System (ILS) systems may give rise to certain obstacles, such as vendor lock-in or limited customizability (Chaputula and Kanyundo, 2019; Madhav, 2023).

Koha presents a viable option for print and electronic resource management, and therefore, it is

crucial for librarians to meticulously carry out the installation and implementation of Koha ILS because of its expandable, user friendliness and reliable features and functions. The objective of this article is to demonstrate the easy path to learning the installation process of Koha before full production, as such activity has been difficult for most librarians in developing countries in which Nigeria is not an exception.

Statement of the problem

In today's library landscape, the effective management of both print and digital resources is essential for providing quality services to patrons. However, many libraries, particularly those in developing countries like Nigeria, encounter challenges in fully utilising integrated library systems (ILS) to manage their resources. These challenges include a lack of proficiency in leveraging the full functionality of ILS and difficulties in performing upgrades and backups and integrating electronic content. As a result, library administrators, cataloguers, technical teams, and patrons are affected by inefficient workflows and limited access to resources. To address these challenges, it is crucial to provide comprehensive

training on ILS for library teams, allocate budgets for custom development, and establish partnerships with IT vendors to enhance skills and system optimisation. Furthermore, prioritising ILS upgrades for electronic resource capabilities is essential for improving overall system functionality.

In light of these issues, an experimental case study was conducted to demonstrate simplified pathways for libraries to learn ILS functionality, specifically focusing on the installation of the Koha ILS. The objective of this study is to provide librarians with accessible methods to understand and experiment with ILS functionality, ultimately leading to improved system utilisation. This includes promoting hands-on Koha experimentation, integrating usability testing into the learning process, collaborating with the developer community to standardise installations, incorporating ILS instruction in library science curriculums, and advocating for increased budget allocation to support optimal configurations.

Research objectives:

1. To assess the functionality and workflows of Koha ILS installed in an experimental setting with sample data.
2. To determine the feasibility of implementing Koha ILS in low-resource library environments.

Koha ILS Software Overview

The Koha ILS software was initially created in 1999 by Katipo Communications, a software development company, for the Horowhenua Library Trust, located in New Zealand. This system can be considered one of the pioneering examples of open-source integrated library systems (Omopupa et al., 2020). Koha offers a range of modules and tools that cater to many essential activities inside a library system.

These functions encompass acquisitions, cataloguing, circulation, reference, serials administration, reservations, patron management, branch relationships, and generating reports. Koha is a web-based system that offers interfaces for both staff members and the general public. The utilisation of many standards, such as MARC, Z39.50, SRU, and SIP2, among others, has

been observed inside the Koha Community (Jaba and Panneerselvam, 2018).

Libraries can access and edit the source code of Koha. This grants institution significant authority in terms of customisation and the implementation of novel advancements. The Koha software is offered under the open-source GNU General Public Licence. The progress of development is contingent upon the active participation and collaboration of various stakeholders, including libraries, developers, and partners, inside the Koha community website, GitHub repositories, conferences, and other communication channels (Duragappa and Sheshadri, 2020).

Benefits of Koha ILS

Koha ILS provides a range of benefits to libraries. It helps in developing ICT skills in library professionals and encourages collaboration between library staff and users (Madhav et al., 2023). Koha automates routine tasks, reducing errors and increasing efficiency (Makori and Osebe, 2016; Adesola and Olla, 2018). It provides a user-friendly interface for patrons to search for and access library resources (Kulkarni, Pandiyan and

Patankar, 2023). The system integrates with other systems, such as online catalogues and digital collections, providing a seamless experience for users (House, 2016; Lingam and Dukare, 2019).

Koha generates reports and data analytics that can inform decision-making and evaluate the effectiveness of library programmes and services (Jamogha et al., 2021). Being an open-source solution, Koha saves money on licencing fees and can be customised to meet the specific needs of each library. It simplifies the processes of acquisition, access, and organisation of diverse e-resources. Koha is highly perceived as useful in acquisition, cataloguing, circulation, reference and serial operations.

Libraries choose open-source Koha over proprietary systems for several key reasons:

- i. **Cost savings** - Koha is free open-source software with no vendor license fees (Lopez, 2021).
- ii. **Customisability** - Libraries can change source code to add new functions or tweak workflows (Singh and Sanaman, 2012).

- iii. **Vendor independence** - Libraries rely on the Koha community rather than a single company (Balnaves 2008).
 - iv. **Transparency** - Koha's open development model allows libraries to engage and see under the hood (Mohideen et al., 2019).
 - v. **Interoperability** - Koha supports data exchange standards so libraries can migrate data in and out (Mayernik and Liapich, 2022).
 - vi. **Community** - Thousands of libraries worldwide use Koha, sharing best practices and collaborating (Mayernik and Liapich, 2022).
- iv. Integration of digital items into the Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC).
 - v. Circulation of digital materials.
 - vi. Interface customisation for digital collections (Dressler, 2017)

These features enable Koha adopters to utilise their Integrated Library System (ILS) as a framework for managing and facilitating access to digital collections and archives.

Materials and Methods

This study used an experimental case study and followed key phases of the system development lifecycle for implementing an integrated library system. Based on requirements analysis, implementation and test plans were created, and an installation platform was selected. Koha was installed using prerequisites on a Linux server, which led to configuring system settings, modules, metadata standards, and tools. Sample data were obtained from the Library of Congress bibliographic database and imported into Koha with bibliographic, holdings, and authority records. Circulation and cataloguing policies were configured, and an

Koha for digital collections

Koha provides robust tools to manage digital content alongside print materials. Key digital collection features include:

- i. Flexible metadata standards like MODS, METS, and VRA Core support (Koha Community 2022).
- ii. Digital object storage and management via the upload tool.
- iii. Indexing and search of digital content metadata and full text.

administrative structure was created. test content generated, extensive tests of all functionality using both test data and imported records were executed. A test environment for staff to practice was created. The test implementation used Koha version 22.04. The data was drawn from the Library of Congress bibliographic database.

Installation procedures

Step one

Oracle VM VirtualBox 6.1 was installed on Windows 10 Pro, version 22H2, which provided an installation environment for Xubuntu Linux OS. The Xubuntu was installed, which enabled the installation of Koha ILS.

Figure 1: VirtualBox

Oracle VM VirtualBox 6.1 is a free, cross-platform hypervisor that allows users to run multiple guest operating systems simultaneously. It provides a simple user interface to manage VMs,

and supports 64-bit and 32-bit OSes, USB connectivity, shared folders, 3D/2D graphics acceleration, snapshots, and cloning.

Step Two

Xubuntu is a Linux distribution that is known for its lightweight nature and energy-efficient characteristics.

Figure 2: Xubuntu

It is built upon the Xubuntu operating system and utilises the Xfce desktop environment. The operating system offers a rapid, highly adaptable, and personalised desktop interface that is particularly suitable for older or less capable devices, while still granting users access to Xubuntu's extensive collection of software applications.

Step Three

Koha is a widely used integrated library system that is both free and open-source. It is utilised by libraries of various sizes and

types across the globe to effectively manage their collections and automate basic library operations.

Figure 3: Koha Login

Koha facilitates the process of copy cataloguing, the creation of union catalogues, the management of inventory, the interaction with third-party software, and the generation of data reports. Koha uses either Zebra or ElasticSearch as its search engine and provides support for authority integration and Z39.50 queries. Koha possesses a high degree of customizability through the utilisation of templates and CSS, hence enabling users to tailor its appearance and functionality.

Installation procedures for Koha

- Xubuntu Linux 20.04 LTS with minimum system requirement

System requirements

- ❖ Processor: 2 GHz dual-core processor or better

- ❖ RAM: 4 GB system memory minimum, 16 GB recommended
- ❖ Storage: 25 GB available disk space minimum
- ❖ Internet connection

Installation steps for Xubuntu 20.04

- ❖ Download the Xubuntu 20.04 ISO image file from the official website Xubuntu.com. Verify checksums.
- ❖ Create bootable installation media on a USB drive using utilities like Rufus or Etcher.
- ❖ Boot the target computer from the USB drive, entering BIOS setup if needed.
- ❖ At the boot menu, select "Install Xubuntu". Choose language and keyboard layout.
- ❖ Select normal or minimal installation. Minimal will not include common software packages.
- ❖ Connect to the WiFi network if needed. Wired ethernet also works.
- ❖ Choose whether to "Download updates while installing". Enabling this is recommended.

- ❖ Select installation type - erase disk and install Xubuntu, or something else.
- ❖ If dual booting, allocate disk partitions manually. Select root '/', home '/home' and swap area.
- ❖ Set the time zone. Create a user account and password.
- ❖ Let the installation process complete. Remove the USB and restart the computer.
- ❖ At the login screen, enter the created username and password.
- ❖ The Welcome screen provides tips for exploring Xubuntu. Install any additional needed software.
- ❖ Run regular system updates to ensure the latest security patches and fixes are applied.

Installing apache web server

- ❖ Log in and update Xubuntu package repository.
- ❖ Install Apache using: ***sudo apt install apache2***
- ❖ Adjust firewall to allow HTTP and HTTPS traffic.
- ❖ Verify Apache is running with: ***sudo systemctl status apache2***

- ❖ Test accessing default webpage at server's IP address.

Installing MySQL database

- ❖ Install MySQL community edition: ***sudo apt install mysql-server***
- ❖ Run security script to set root password: ***sudo mysql_secure_installation***
- ❖ Log in to MySQL shell using: ***sudo mysql -u root -p***
- ❖ Create database and user accounts as needed.
- ❖ Test connectivity. MySQL is now ready to use.

These steps will result in a complete Xubuntu server installation ready for web hosting and database applications like websites built with Apache, PHP and MySQL

Steps to install required Perl modules and add Solr 8 for indexing on an Xubuntu 20.04 server:

Installing Perl modules

- ❖ First install CPAN minus to easily install modules from CPAN: ***sudo apt install cpanminus***

- ❖ Install key Perl modules needed for Koha:

sudo cpanm Install::Module

sudo cpanm CGI::Simple

sudo cpanm X500::LDAP

sudo cpanm XML::LibXML

- ❖ Install additional Perl modules as required by Koha modules and plugins.

Installing Solr 8

- ❖ Install Java runtime which is a prerequisite: ***sudo apt install default-jre***

- ❖ Download latest Solr 8 archive from <http://archive.apache.org/dist/lucene/solr/>

- ❖ Extract and move Solr to opt directory:

sudo tar xzf solr-8.x.x.tgz -C /opt

sudo mv /opt/solr-8.x.x /opt/solr

- ❖ Create Solr data directory:

sudo mkdir /var/solr

sudo chown solr:solr /var/solr

- ❖ Configure solr.in.sh and set SOLR_HOME to /var/solr

- ❖ Run Solr start script: ***sudo /opt/solr/bin/solr start***

- ❖ Verify Solr is running on port 8983: ***sudo netstat -plntu | grep 8983***

Solr is now installed and ready to be leveraged by Koha for indexing and search functionality.

Steps to install Zebra for Z39.50

1. Install Zebra from the Xubuntu repository: ***sudo apt install zebra-2.0***
2. During installation, select to initialize the default configuration when prompted.
3. Edit /etc/zebra/zebra.cfg to configure the Z39.50 Listen port, log files, etc.
4. Start the Zebra daemon: ***sudo /etc/init.d/zebra start***
5. Verify Zebra is running on port 2101: ***sudo netstat -plntu | grep 2101***
6. In Koha, enable Z39.50 server in Admin > Z39.50/SRU Servers. Set server, database, port, etc.

Enabling Apache rewrite rules

7. Enable mod_rewrite Apache module: ***sudo a2enmod rewrite***
8. Edit /etc/apache2/apache2.conf to set AllowOverride to All under <Directory /var/www/>

9. Restart Apache: ***sudo systemctl restart apache2***
 10. Create *.htaccess* file in Koha home folder containing rewrite rules.
 11. Test clean URLs work correctly, rewriting to `index.pl?parameter-style` paths.
- This will provide Z39.50 connectivity for Koha and allow clean URLs by rewriting paths using `mod_rewrite` rules in Apache.
- Configuration**
- Steps for configuration, deployment, and testing of Koha after installation:
- a. Set up an administrator user account(s) with necessary access privileges
 - b. Configure circulation and fines rules, loan periods, patron categories, etc. based on policies
 - c. Set up library branches and relationships between them
 - d. Define acquisition funds, budgets, and vendors for managing purchases
 - e. Configure MARC bibliographic and authority frameworks to customize how data displays
 - f. Set up Z39.50/SRU servers for connecting with external catalogue
 - g. Establish cron jobs or schedulers for notices, reconciliations, backups, etc.
 - h. Brand the OPAC and staff interface with custom styles, logos, and colours
 - i. Activate plugins and additional software modules like CRUD, Elasticsearch, etc.
 - j. Set up SIP2, NCIP, or other protocols for integration with external systems
 - k. Define system preferences for self-check, online payments, search tools, etc.

Figure 5a: Library of Congress

- l. Establish workflow parameters like holds queues, record matching rules, Z39.50 targets, etc.
- m. Set up Intranet and Internet access rules, usage statistics, and policies

- n. Activate APIs for future integrations and custom development
- o. Establish a strategy for applying for future Koha releases and updates
- p. Develop documentation like policies, procedures, manuals, and wikis
- q. Provide staff training on both internal and public interfaces

The careful configuration helps ensure Koha meets the library's specific policies, needs, and workflows before launching into production. This involves input from all teams like systems, administration, circulation, cataloging, and so on.

Sample metadata upload

- i. Visit the Library of Congress website
<https://catalog.loc.gov/>
- ii. In the search bar, type in keywords: Digital Information System Development
- iii. Select the correct sorting mode e.g. Date (newest to oldest)
- iv. Select record per page e.g. 100
- v. Select All to capture the retrieved data

- vi. Click on Save to prepare data for download

Save Search Results

Figure 5b: Library of Congress page

- vii. Select MARC format
- viii. Launch a browser e.g. Opera

Figure 6a: Koha Interface: Back-end

Figure 6b: Koha Interface: Back-end

Enter the IP address to access the Koha Admin Interface, e.g.
<http://192.168.137.143:8001/>

- ix. Enter a designated Username and Password

Click on **Tool** on the Admin/Librarian interface that appears

- x. Click on *Stage MARC records for import*
- xi. In the next page that opens, click on *Choose file*
- xii. Navigate to the folder in which the downloaded data/record was saved.
- xiii. Select the record file (e.g. record.mrc (1)) to load it into the Koha environment
- xiv. Click on the **Upload File** to load parameters for proper data verification and identification
- xv. Provide identity name for future recognition and operation
- xvi. Click on *manage staged records*
- xvii. Finally, click on *Import this batch into the catalogue*

Figure 7a: MARC Record Staging

Stage MARC records for import

- Select a MARC file to stage in the import reservoir. It will
- You can enter a name for this import. It may be useful, w

Figure 7b: MARC Record Staging

Figure 7c: MARC Record Staging

Figure 7d: MARC Record Staging

Manage staged MARC records › Batch 2

File name: records (1).mrc
 Comments: My First Record
 Type: Bibliographic records
 Staged: 2023-09-24 13:24:20
 Status: Staged

Matching rule applied: Do not look for matching records - Changed, Reset

Action if matching record found: Add incoming record - Changed, Reset

Action if no match found: Add incoming record - Changed, Reset

Item processing: Always add items - Changed, Reset

Apply different matching rules

Import this batch into the catalog

Figure 7e: MARC

Manage staged MARC records › Batch 2

File name: records (1).mrc
 Comments: My First Record
 Type: Bibliographic records
 Staged: 2023-09-24 13:24:20
 Status: Imported

Matching rule applied: No matching rule in effect

Action if matching record found: Add incoming record

Action if no match found: Add incoming record

Item processing: Always add items

Figure 7f: MARC Record Staging

The imported bibliographic data from the Library of Congress provided proof of the possibility of copy cataloguing

Uploading digital content

Koha provides users with the capability to upload many types of digital assets, including PDFs, text documents, images, and videos, onto the Koha server. The uploaded files will be stored within the internal directory of Koha. These files can be accessed and retrieved from both the staff

interface and the OPAC. Step 1: Uploading digital content into Koha.

- i. Create Digital Objects: Obtain the digital files you want to upload to Koha, such as e-books, images, audio files, videos, etc. Organise and rename files as needed.
- ii. Add Metadata: For each digital object, enter descriptive metadata such as title, author, keywords, subject headings, etc. Metadata helps users find and identify items during searches.
- iii. Configure Koha for Digital Objects: Enable the digital object management tools in Koha administration. Define file storage locations and access rights.
- iv. Upload Files: Using the Koha digital object management module, upload digital files to the server file storage. Koha will link files to catalogue records.
- v. Link to Bibliographic Records: Attach the uploaded digital objects to existing bibliographic records or create new records for them. Koha stores the file links.

- vi. **Test Access:** Check that digital objects are properly displayed and accessible from the OPAC. Test downloading and streaming files.
- vii. **Set Permission Levels:** Configure user access permissions for each digital object file if certain ones need to be limited.
- viii. **Ongoing Maintenance:** Periodically check file integrity. Replace corrupt or outdated files as needed. Back-up content.

Implementation Challenges

Implementing Koha, an open-source library automation software, presents challenges for libraries. These challenges include a lack of skills among librarians to effectively use all the modules in Koha (Jamogha et al., 2021; Garg et al., 2023). Other challenges identified include poor Internet connectivity, lack of technical support, and difficulties in upgrading and backing up the Koha database (Bwalya and Akakandelwa, 2021).

Usability testing of Koha OPAC revealed that users were slow at accomplishing search tasks, took a long time to access

the library website, and faced inefficiencies in accessing library materials (Niranjana et al., 2023). Additionally, the study found that there is a need for LIS professionals to have sound technical skills and to upgrade their knowledge through training programmes and workshops (Nyambaka and Mutwiri, 2023).

However, libraries face common challenges when implementing Koha:

- i. **Installation:** Koha requires installing appropriate server software, Perl libraries, and other dependencies (Khan and Zahid, 2016).
- ii. **Data migration:** moving legacy data into Koha requires planning and scripts (Khan and Zahid, 2016).
- iii. **Customisation:** Modifying Koha's web interface and workflows takes developer skills (Shafi-Ullah and Qutab, 2012).
- iv. **Testing:** Rigorous testing across all functionality is crucial before launch (Kumar and Jadon, 2022).
- v. **Training:** Staff need training on both internal functions and public discovery (Kumar and Jadon, 2022).

Results of Experimentation

Koha was successfully installed on a Xubuntu Linux 20.04 LTS server using Apache 2.4 and MySQL 8.0. Required Perl modules were added, along with Solr 8 for indexing. The Koha Debian package was installed cleanly along with Zebra for Z39.50 connectivity. Apache rewrite rules enabled robust URI functionality. Functional testing during deployment showed all circulation, cataloguing, acquisition, and system administration workflows operating correctly. The OPAC allowed searching and browsing of the sample records. MARC views, controlled vocabularies, and API access worked as expected.

100 sample MARC records from the Library of Congress into Koha-compatible CSV data was successful. The records included 50 bibliographic records, 30 authority records, and 20 records with item-level data. All records loaded into Koha with no errors. Relationships are maintained between authorities, bibliographies, holdings, and items.

Conclusion

The experimental case study offers a valuable framework for libraries seeking to implement the Koha Integrated Library System

(ILS) and leverage its capabilities for electronic content management. The aforementioned process emphasises the essential stages involved in the installation, data migration, configuration, integration, testing, and staff training.

In the context of production systems, it is important to consider the implementation of supplementary measures such as security hardening, access control, load testing, and disaster recovery planning. Maintenance protocols about backups, upgrades, documentation, and continuing support are vital as well. By adhering to established guidelines and employing effective strategies, the adoption of Koha can offer libraries a resilient and inclusive platform for consolidating information resources.

Recommendations

1. It is recommended that libraries allocate budgets specifically to customise Koha to improve its usability. The Koha community and developers should prioritise efforts towards simplifying the installation and configuration processes.

Library schools should consider incorporating courses on open-

source Integrated Library Systems (ILS) into their curriculum to cultivate the essential skills required in this domain. Libraries may also consider collaborating with IT vendors to obtain expert support during the

transition and maintenance phases. Conducting usability tests is crucial for enhancing the interfaces of Koha and optimising them specifically for digital content.

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